

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The partners of EuroCC@Greece[^] are providing a series of HPC services* for Academia, Industry and Public sector under the scope of EuroCC*. The current document is a tracking of the publications that were supported and sponsored by EuroCC@Greece** and it is intended to be updated regularly. The list is presented per use case.

[^] <https://eurocc-greece.gr/>

^{*} <https://zenodo.org/records/10025329>

^{*} <https://www.eurocc-access.eu>

^{**} <https://eurocc-greece.gr/use-cases/>

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LISTPER USE CASE

Advancements in Predictive Modeling of Structural Behaviors through Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning Techniques

- Markou, N. Bakas, S. Chatzichristofis, and M. Papadrakakis, "A general framework of high-performance machine learning algorithms: application in structural mechanics," *Comput. Mech.* *Accept.* August 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00466-023-02386-9>
- Duan Calitz, George Markou, Nikolaos Bakas, and Manolis Papadrakakis. "Developing fundamental period formulae for steel framed structures". In: *9th International Conference on Computational Methods in Structural Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*. COMPDYN 2023, Athens, Greece, June 2023. url: <https://2023.compdyn.org/>.
- Vistor Chibaya, George Markou, Nikolaos Bakas, and Manolis Papadrakakis. "Development of formulae for the section rotations due to bending of curved steel i-beams through ai and ml algorithms". In: *9th International Conference on Computational Methods in Structural Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*. COMPDYN 2023, Athens, Greece, June 2023. url: <https://2023.compdyn.org/>.
- Ashley Megan van der Westhuizen, George Markou, Nikolaos Bakas, and Manolis Papadrakakis. "Developing an artificial neural network model that predicts the fundamental period of steel structures using a large dataset". In: *9th International Conference on Computational Methods in Structural Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*. COMPDYN 2023, Athens, Greece, June 2023. url: <https://2023.compdyn.org/>.
- K T Braun, N Bakas, G Markou, and S W Jacobsz. "Advanced numerical modelling of the nonlinear mechanical behaviour of a laterally loaded pile embedded in stiff unsaturated clay". en. In: *Journal of the South African Institution of Civil Engineering* 65 (June 2023), pp. 28–38. issn: 1021-2019. url: <http://www.scielo.org.za/scielo.php?script=sciarttext&pid=S1021-20192023000200004&nrm=iso>.
- Westhuizen, G. Markou, and N. Bakas, "Use of ai and ml algorithms in developing closed-form formulae, for structural engineering design," in *Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning Techniques for Civil Engineering*, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.igi-global.com/chapter/use-of-ai-and-ml-algorithms-in-developing-closed-form-formulae-for-structural-engineering-design/324541>

LINK: <https://eurocc-greece.gr/advancements-in-predictive-modeling-of-structural-behaviors-through-artificial-intelligence-and-machine-learning-techniques/>

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LISTPER USE CASE

Analyzing shotgun metagenomic datasets of EMO BON stations

- Haris Zafeiropoulos, Martin Beracochea, Stelios Ninidakis, Katrina Exter, Antonis Potirakis, Gianluca De Moro, Lorna Richardson, Erwan Corre, João Machado, Evangelos Pafilis, Georgios Kotoulas, Ioulia Santi, Robert D Finn, Cymon J Cox, Christina Pavloudi, 2023. metaGOflow: a workflow for the analysis of marine Genomic Observatories shotgun metagenomics data. *GigaScience*, 12, p.giad078. Available on:
<https://academic.oup.com/gigascience/article/doi/10.1093/gigascience/giad078/7321054>

LINK:<https://eurocc-greece.gr/analyzing-shotgun-metagenomic-datasets-of-emo-bon-stations/>

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GENERAL PUBLICATIONS

- Karozis, S., Bakas, N., Kanellou, E., Psarianou, A., Kakavas, T., & Hatzakis, I. (2023). Developing HPC services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10025329>
- Karozis, S., Ziouvelou, X., & Karkaletsis, V. (2023). Mapping the national HPC ecosystem and training needs: The Greek paradigm. The Journal of Supercomputing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-023-05080-y>
- Ziouvelou, X., Karozis, S., & Karkaletsis, V. (2022). Training Needs for HPC, HPDA, AI, HPAI in Greece - 2022 Report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10477980>

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ABOUT US

Contact us at

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A National Competence Center is the reference and single point of contact and coordination on a national level for HPC. Its missions are to analyse, implement and coordinate all necessary activities and offer services to end users to cover their needs: from access to resources and technological consultancy to the provision of training courses for academia, public administrations and industry.

The aim is to bring together the necessary expertise to set up a cross-European network of NCCs in HPC-related topics with 31 participating members and associated states and to provide a broad service portfolio tailored to the respective national needs of academia, public administrations and industry. Each NCC has a presentation page with their skills and contact information.

EuroCC@Greece is one of the 33 HPC Competence Centres, built in the framework of the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU).

The overall objective of the Greek National Competence Center is to enable the efficient uptake of HPC technologies with the 3-fold goal to:

1. advance competitiveness in research
2. improve effectiveness of government services and
3. promote innovation in industry.

In order to achieve this goal, the NCC will address the issues of training and skills development, technology transfer, collaboration with Industry, competence mapping and awareness raising, in the fields of High Performance Computing, High Performance Data Analytics, Artificial Intelligence and Big Data.

Consortium

The Greek National Competence Center "EuroCC@Greece", is run by a consortium of 5 institutions, namely

- National Infrastructures for Research and Technology (GRNET)
- National Center for Scientific Research "Demokritos" (NCSR)
- Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas (FORTH)
- Institute of Communication and Computer Systems of NTUA (ICCS)
- Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)

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